

FATIGUE EVALUATION OF STRUCTURAL PHENOLIC SANDWICHES STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the static and fatigue flexural behaviour of sandwich structures including glass/phenolic skins. Three core materials (balsa, PMI foam and phenolic corrugations) and two moulding processes (RTM and hand lay up with vacuum bag) are investigated. The static properties and damage mechanism are very different in function of the core material. The fatigue limit is estimated with the S-N curves and static post-fatigue tests. This fatigue limit shows differences between the two moulding processes.

INTRODUCTION

The sandwich technologies and applications expand quickly in the transport fields [1]. The aeronautics already use sandwich constructions successfully in structural parts. The calculation of sandwich structures are now easier with the use of the finite elements code. However, the fatigue behavior of sandwich is still unknown and this field is rather absent of the literature.

This study deals with the fatigue behavior of sandwich structures. Three sandwiches structures and two moulding technologies are investigated in fatigue bending tests. The processes are the RTM (Resin Transfer Moulding) and the hand lay up technology with vacuum bag pressure during the cure. These processes bring about different results in term of adhesion quality between the skins and the core material and in term of fatigue life of the sandwich structure.

The use of phenolic resin produces a very good fire, smoke and toxicity behavior. Usually this resin is not used in structural parts. In this paper, we study different sandwich structures composed of glass/phenolic skins and balsa, PMI (Polymethacrylimid) expanded foam or corrugated core (hat type of glass/phenolic plus phenolic foam).

This study defines the damage processes during the fatigue bending tests. These damage processes are included in the core and at the skins/core interfaces. The way to damage the structure is very different in function of the core material and the bending axis (longitudinal or transverse).

Figure 1. The three different sandwich structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

SANDWICH STRUCTURES

The studied sandwich structures are composed of glass/phenolic skins and three different core materials. These core materials are balsa (150kg/m^3), PMI expanded foam (80kg/m^3) and hat type corrugated core (phenolic foam (100kg/m^3) included in glass/phenolic corrugations). The three types of sandwiches are illustrated with the figure 1.

Two moulding technologies are investigated in this study. On one hand a classic RTM process (A) is used to produce a glass content in the sandwich skins between 35 and 40% in volume ; on the other hand the hand lay up process (B) is used with pressure from a vacuum bag during the cure. This second process produces a glass content of the skins of the sandwich structures between 55 and 60 volume percents. A total of six different sandwich structures are moulded with skins composed of glass fibers and phenolic matrix. The global thickness of the sandwiches is 60mm. The two skins sequences are $[(0.90)/0^6/(0.90)]$ for the PMI foam and balsa core sandwich. The corrugated sandwich structure has $[(0.90)/0^5/(0.90)]$ skins and $[\pm 45]$ glass/phenolic corrugations. The corrugations for the sandwich moulded with the process A are composed of two $[\pm 45]$ plies and with the A process only one ply is present. More details about the corrugations and the skins are given elsewhere by Barré et al [2].

If the balsa and the PMI foam are well known as core materials for sandwich structures, the corrugated core is the result of previous studies and optimization. The choice in the parameters of the corrugation is guided by the work of Barré et al [3] which offers optimization of the corrugation angle, the corrugation thickness, the basic cell period and the foam density. The corrugated sandwich structures take into account the numerical study previously mentioned and the difficulties in the moulding process.

TEST METHOD

The sandwich constructions are used in flexural loads. There is several ways to test sandwich structures in bending, but the easier and the most common are the three and the four points bending tests. The second test (e.g. four points bending) has the advantage to offer a central area loaded with a pure flexural moment and two side areas loaded with flexural moment mixed with shear load. This test clearly shows two different behaviour of the structure. This is the reason why the evaluation of the sandwich structures is conducted in four points bending (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Load conditions of the four points bending.

The four points bending tests are performed on specimens cut in sandwich plates of $1\text{m} \times 1\text{m}$. The width of the specimens is about 100mm except in the Longi case of the corrugated sandwich where the width is the period of the basic corrugation cell.

The sandwiches are evaluated in static bending tests to measure the reference values of elastic and failure behaviour. Then the fatigue bending tests are performed in the same load configuration. The static tests are conducted at a cross head speed of 2mm/min and the fatigue one at the frequency of 4 Hz. The control in fatigue is made with the load and the R ratio for fatigue tests ($R = F_{\text{min}}/F_{\text{max}}$) is equal to 0.1 during the fatigue test.

The experimental configuration is equipped with displacement sensor where the load is applied. During the beginning of the study, a middle displacement sensor was used to try to determine the intrinsic flexural rigidities values of D_{11} and D_{22} . This measure was shown to be very difficult by Barré et al [2], then during the fatigue tests this middle sensor was not used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The static and fatigue flexural results are presented here. For practical reasons, the maximum load (F_{max}) and the rigidity ratio $F/(\delta \cdot b)$, in N/mm^2 , (F : load applied ; δ : central deflection) are produced for a width (b) of 1mm.

STATIC TEST

The results of the static bending tests conducted on the different sandwich structures are presented in terms of elastic, damage and failure behaviour. The load-deflection curves show the global behaviour of the different sandwiches (Fig.3-5). The main parameters are presented in Fig.6-7 to appreciate the great difference between the three core materials. These main parameters are the maximum force, the ratio of the load divided per the central deflection (representative of the global rigidity).

Figure 3. Static bending behaviour of the balsa core sandwich structures.

Figure 4. Static bending behaviour of the PMI foam core sandwich structures.

Figure 5. Static bending behaviour of the corrugated core sandwich structures.

The bending behaviour observed during the experimental tests and the Fig.3-5 allow us to bring several remarks on the elastic behaviour and on the failure process of the sandwich structures.

Elastic behaviour

The balsa core sandwich is shown to be the more rigid in the two main axis. We can point out that the corrugated sandwich structure has an equal rigidity to the balsa core one with the RTM moulding process. The difference between the two processes is quite small except in the case of corrugated core sandwich structure. This difference is explained by the constitution of the corrugation between the two processes (e.g. 1 ply [± 45] in the B process and 2 plies for A). The elastic behaviour is almost completely linear in the corrugated and in the balsa core sandwich, but the PMI foam core sandwich shows non-linear elastic behaviour.

Figure 6. Bending rigidity ratio results of the sandwich structures in the two axis.

Damage and failure behaviour

The damage development in the several sandwich structures is completely different. In all the sandwich structures, the area where the flexural moment is invariable is still undamaged even when the structure has failed.

The damage process of the corrugated sandwich has already been studied by Barré et al [2] with cycles of loading and deloading the specimen to measure the evolution of the sandwich rigidity. The damage mechanisms in the Trans direction are the shear crack in the phenolic foam, the interface foam/skins or corrugations failure, the delamination between the corrugation and the skin and the buckling of the corrugation (Fig.7). The damage process is contained in few cells located in the mixed shear/flexural moment areas in the four points bending specimen. The failure mechanism in the Longi case is the shear buckling of corrugations in the shear zone of the specimen. This mechanism explains the difference between the two processes for the Longi corrugated sandwich structure because of the only one [± 45] ply in the A process case.

Figure 7. Damage process of phenolic corrugated sandwich in the Trans axis

Figure 8. Damage process of balsa core sandwich.

In the balsa core sandwich, the failure mechanism is very simple and is the same in the axis. This mechanism is a shear crack in the core material which leads to delaminations between the core and the skin on the top of the sandwich on one side of the balsa crack and on the bottom on the other side (Fig.8). This failure is unexpected and liberate an important quantity

of elastic energy which produces great delamination areas. The location of this shear failure is guided by the heterogeneity of the balsa material. In fact the balsa is composed of several pieces of wood glued together to produce a medium nominal density ; but the density of the balsa piece can vary from half to twice of the nominal density. Then the balsa cores have weak areas which failed by shear cracks. The evolution of the rigidity during the four points bending tests was shown to be zero until the failure of the structure.

The PMI foam core sandwich also has the same failure mode in the two main axis. This failure can be of a different kind : indentation of the sandwich by flexural tools, shear crack in the foam and delamination between skin and core material or even delamination in buckling when bad adhesion quality was found between core and skins. The shear cracks in the core material and the skin/core delaminations produce if the adhesion is of poor quality (e.g. process A). In the B process, the better foam/skin interface quality only conducts to local failure mode (e.g. buckling of the foam and indentation of the skins) just above the flexural tools which have 60mm of diameter. This mode shows that this sandwich structure has a good homogeneity even if it is composed of two very different materials (core and skins).

Figure 9. Bending maximum load results of the sandwich structures in the two axis.

The maximum load per unit of width is quite constant in the balsa and in the PMI foam core sandwich structures (Fig. 9). This load is rather low in the Trans axis for the corrugated structure and for this sandwich the difference in the corrugation composition has an important effect on the maximum supported load.

The balsa sandwich structures have good static behaviour compared to the other structures. The failure mode, unexpected because of the important variation of the density in the core material, leads to take great safety factor to design a structure. The PMI foam core sandwich can also produce unexpected failures if the adhesion quality between the core material and the skins is not perfect. The corrugated sandwich structures have lower maximum load supported in the Trans axis, but after the first damage mechanisms the load supported is still increasing. The damage process extends to next cells when the load increases. The damage is slowed down by corrugations which could be considered as barriers in the sandwich structure because they ensure the link between the two skins of the sandwich structure.

FATIGUE TESTS

The evaluation of the sandwich structures in fatigue four points bending tests was conducted in all the structures presented in the static parts except for the balsa and PMI foam core sandwiches in the Trans axis.

S-N curves

The S-N curves are presented (Fig.10-12) in percent of the static maximum load for each sandwich structure. These figures also show the tendency when the specimen has not failed at the number of cycles identified in function of the static test post fatigue. The arrows added to the markers in the Fig. 10-12 mean that the specimen has not failed at the number of cycles plotted. The horizontal arrow means that no post fatigue test was conducted. If a static post fatigue test was performed, the arrow is climbing, if the post fatigue properties were equal or superior to the static one and in the opposite case (e.g. inferior properties) the arrow decreases.

Figure 10. S-N curve of PMI core sandwich structure in fatigue bending

Figure 11. S-N curve of balsa core sandwich structure in fatigue bending

Figure 12. S-N curve of corrugated core sandwich structure in fatigue bending.

These S-N curves give a very good idea of the fatigue properties of the sandwich structures. The fatigue limit could be estimated by the values presented in Tab. 1 with caution. These results show clearly that the B process gives a better fatigue behaviour in percents of the maximum static load. This conclusion could be explained by the difference of glass content between the two processes as Konur et al [4] explained in their review concerning the fatigue performance of composite materials. The B process produces moulding conditions with efficient compression of the sandwich structure which allows better adhesion quality between the core material and the skins. Thus this compression decreases the number of defects (porosities, etc...) which are very injurious in long term fatigue test.

In function of the core material, the variation of this estimated fatigue limit is not so different. The balsa core sandwich presents a lot of variability in the results and some accident could happen if very low density balsa is present in the specimen (Fig.11). This variability of the sandwich with balsa core discards this notion of fatigue limit.

Table 1. Fatigue limits evaluation of sandwich structures.

	Process A	Process B
Balsa / Longi	35 %	≈ 50 %
Balsa / Trans	35 %	xx
PMI / Longi	45 %	70 %
PMI / Trans	> 40 %	xx
Corrugated / Longi	40 %	60 %
Corrugated / Trans	40 %	50 %

The damage processes during the fatigue tests are similar to the processes during the static tests. Thus the evolution of the rigidity during the fatigue tests is insignificant in the balsa, in the PMI foam and in the Longi corrugated core material sandwich. There is, only, the Trans corrugated sandwich structure for which the rigidity clearly decreases. This point has already been described by Barré et al [3].

Then in the case of the sandwich structures studied here, the fatigue performance is not measurable by the loss of the rigidity because of the way of loading the specimen. The fatigue performance (e.g. life) can be reduced in an important rate if defects are present (e.g. mainly bad skin/core adhesion quality).

CONCLUSION

This study evaluates the static and fatigue performances of glass/phenolic skins sandwich structures with three different core materials and two moulding processes. The influence of the core material is of prime importance for the elastic and failure behaviour. The balsa sandwich produces unexpected failure with great dispersion, the PMI foam sandwich structure is very influenced by the adhesion quality produced by the moulding process between the skins and the core. The corrugated sandwich structure is very strong in the Longi axis and the damage evolution progresses in the basic cells in the Trans axis. The fatigue tests and static post fatigue campaign reveal an important variation of the fatigue limit between the two moulding processes in normalized values.

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